

Appendix A: Images and graphs

Fig. A.1. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G003.8+0.3 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G003.8+0.3 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.09, 0.14 and 0.19 Jy beam $^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and gridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.2. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G018.8+0.3 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G018.8+0.3 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.33, 0.8 and 1.5 Jy beam $^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.3. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G021.8-0.6 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G021.8-0.6 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.4, 1.5 and 2.9 Jy beam^{-1} related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.4. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G022.7-00.2 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). The yellow circles indicate the four H II regions G022.724-00.010 (1), G022.730-00.239 (2), G022.757-00.246 (3) and G022.780-00.401 (4) cataloged as ‘known’ by Anderson et al. (2014) (discovery author Anderson et al. 2011), and resolved in our SMGPS image. *Bottom:* G022.7-00.2 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at $0.6, 0.9$ and 1.1 Jy beam^{-1} related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.5. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G023.3-0.3 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). The yellow circles indicate the four H II regions G023.423-00.216 (1), G023.389-00.148 (2), G023.439-00.187 (3) and G023.438-00.241 (4) cataloged as ‘known’ (in the case of 1 and 2, Sewilo et al. 2004, Anderson et al. 2011) and “groups” (3, 4) by Anderson et al. (2014), and barely resolved in our SMGPS image. *Bottom:* G023.3-0.3 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.4, 1.05 and 1.5 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.6. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G024.7-00.6 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G024.7-00.6 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.1, 0.2 and 0.5 Jy beam $^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.7. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G032.8-0.1 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*upper left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*upper right*). The yellow circles indicate the five H II regions G032.823+00.072 (1), G032.835+00.017 (2), G032.775-00.048 (3), G032.749-00.065 (4) and G032.761-00.151 (5) cataloged as ‘known’ (1, 2 and 5, Anderson et al. 2011) and “candidate” (3, 4) by Anderson et al. (2014) (1, 2, 4 and 5) and (Anderson et al. 2015) (3), and resolved in our SMGPS image. *Bottom:* G032.8-0.1 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.09, 0.3 and 0.55 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.8. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G033.2-0.6 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G033.2-0.6 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.06, 0.16 and 0.25 Jy beam^{-1} related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.9. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G035.6-00.4 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G035.6-00.4 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.03, 0.27 and 0.5 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.10. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G040.5-00.5 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G040.5-00.5 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.06, 0.18 and 0.29 Jy beam $^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.11. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G045.7-00.4 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G045.7-00.4 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.07, 0.14 and $0.32 \text{ Jy beam}^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.12. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G046.8-00.3 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G046.8-00.3 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.4, 0.8 and 1.0 Jy beam^{-1} related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.13. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G51.21+0.11 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left*) and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G51.21+0.11 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.4, 0.8 and 1.0 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.14. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G286.5-01.2 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G286.5-01.2 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 Jy beam^{-1} related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.15. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G289.7-00.3 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz *Right*. *Bottom:* G289.7-00.3 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range *Left* and related error map *Right*. This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.12, 0.17 and $0.27 \text{ Jy beam}^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.16. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G290.1-0.8 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. The yellow circle indicate the H II region G290.215-00.814 cataloged as "radio quiet" by Anderson et al. (2014), and barely detected in our SMGPS image. The white box encloses the PWN associated with the SNR G290.1-0.8, which is well resolved in the SMGPS image as shown in the bottom-left zoom box. *Left*) and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G290.1-0.8 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.28, 0.99 and 2.2 Jy beam $^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.17. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G291.0-0.1 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G291.0-0.1 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.05, 0.35 and 1.23 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.18. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G292.2-0.5 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz (*Left*) and GLEAM at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). The yellow circle indicates the location of the parent pulsar PSR J1119-6127. *Bottom:* G292.2-0.5 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.16, 0.28 and 0.45 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.19. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G293.8+0.6 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G293.8+0.6 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.025, 0.12 and 0.18 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.20. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G296.7-0.9 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G296.7-0.9 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.035, 0.14 and 0.23 Jy beam $^{-1}$ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.21. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G296.8-0.3 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left*) and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G296.8-0.3 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.1, 0.23, and 0.5 Jy beam^{-1} related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.22. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G301.4-1.0 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G301.4-1.0 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.01, 0.055 and 0.1 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.23. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G332.4+0.1 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G332.4+0.1 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.2, 0.7 and 1.15 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.24. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G335.2+0.1 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G335.2+0.1 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.09, 0.23 and 0.37 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.25. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G337.3+1.0 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G337.3+1.0 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.15, 0.5 and 0.82 Jy beam^{-1} related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.26. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G348.7+0.3 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G348.7+0.3 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.2, 0.8 and 2.0 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.27. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G351.7+0.8 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G351.7+0.8 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.1, 0.225 and 0.29 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.28. *Upper:* radio images of the SNR G351.9+0.1 carried out with SMGPS at 1.284 GHz. *Left* and MWA at 0.155 GHz (*Right*). *Bottom:* G351.9+0.1 spectral index map produced from SMGPS and GLEAM in the 0.155-1.284 GHz frequency range (*Left*) and related error map (*Right*). This map is created by masking the 0.155 and 1.284 GHz images below the threshold of 4σ of the rms. The contours indicate the intensity levels at 0.05, 0.09 and 0.2 Jy beam⁻¹ related to the SMGPS map convolved and regridded to the GLEAM beam and pixel size.

Fig. A.29. Integrated spectra and related fits of the SNRs G003.8+0.3, G018.8+0.3, G021.8-0.6, G022.7-0.2, G023.3-0.3 and G024.7-0.6. G018.8+0.3: we excluded the lowest frequency point at 0.031 GHz from the fit. G021.8-0.6: we have not considered the low frequency points at 0.0299, 0.0309 and 0.0575 GHz, and we fitted the remaining data both with a simple power-law (black line) and an exponential cut-off model (gray line). G022.7-0.2: we excluded MWA and 0.0575 GHz points from the fit. G023.3-0.3: we excluded from the fit the points below the 0.201 GHz and the literature data with very low, and probably underestimated uncertainties at 1.414, 2.695 and 5 GHz (black line). The gray line is the simple power-law fit restricted to our SMGPS and GLEAM data. G024.7-0.6: the simple power-law fit refers only to the SMGPS and the GLEAM data.

Fig. A.30. Integrated spectra and related fits of the SNRs G032.8-0.1, G033.2-0.6, G035.6-0.4, G040.5-0.5, G045.7-0.6, G046.8-0.3. G040.5-0.5: we excluded from the fit the points at 0.0309, 0.083, 0.111 GHz. We applied both a simple power law (black line, we excluded the point at 8.35 GHz from the fit) and power-law with exponential cut-off fit model (gray line). G045.7-0.6: we excluded from the fit the points at 0.102, 0.327 and 0.960 GHz.

Fig. A.31. Integrated spectra and related fit of the SNRs G051.04+0.07, G286.5-1.2, G289.7-0.3, G290.1-0.8, G291.0-0.1, G292.2-0.5. G290.1-0.8: we excluded from the fit the low-frequency data at 0.0299 and 0.085 GHz. G291.0-0.1: the fit only refers to the SMGPS and GLEAM data.

Fig. A.32. Integrated spectra and related fit of the SNRs G293.8+0.6, G296.7-0.9, G296.8-0.3, G301.4-1.0, G332.4+0.1 and G335.2+0.1. G332.4+0.1: we excluded from the fit the the point at 0.086 GHz.

Fig. A.33. Integrated spectra and related fit of the SNRs G337.3+1.0, G348.7+0.3, G348.7+0.3, G351.7+0.8, G351.9+0.1. G348.7+0.3: we reported both the integrated spectrum of the flux densities estimated from the historical SNR extraction region (including the bright shell, the southern plateau and the eastern filamentary region), and that obtained from SMGPS and GLEAM data by considering the only remnant shell.

Fig. A.34. Spatially resolved spectral study for each SNRs through (in order starting from left): histogram of the spectral index values across the remnant; SMGPS brightness as a function of the spectral index; MWA brightness as a function of the spectral index; scatter plot between the SMGPS and GLEAM brightness.

Fig. A.35. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.36. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.37. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.38. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.39. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.40. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.41. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.42. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.43. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.44. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.45. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.46. Same as Fig.A.34.

Fig. A.47. Same as Fig.A.34.

Appendix B: Tables

Table B.1. Flux density measurements and rms related to the SMGPS (MeerKAT) and GLEAM (MWA) maps of each target. In the last three columns, we report in the order: the integrated spectral index (α_{lit}) from the literature as reported in the Green (2022) catalog; the spectral index (α_{int}) obtained from the integrated spectra analyzed in this work (Figs. A.29-A.33); the spectral index ($\alpha_{0.155-1.284}$) obtained as the mean value of the spectral index map (the reported uncertainty is the related standard deviation).

Source name	Telescope	Freq. (GHz)	Flux density (Jy)	σ (mJy/beam)	α_{lit}	α_{int}	$\alpha_{0.155-1.284}$
G003.8+0.3	MeerKAT	1.284	4.8 ± 0.9	5.46	-0.6	-0.39 ± 0.08	-0.26 ± 0.09
	MWA	0.088	10.5 ± 1.0	159.0			
	MWA	0.119	9.4 ± 0.8	73.1			
	MWA	0.155	6.9 ± 0.6	49.6			
	MWA	0.201	5.8 ± 0.5	31.1			
G018.8+0.3	MeerKAT	1.284	26.3 ± 2.1	0.3	-0.46	-0.41 ± 0.04	-0.45 ± 0.06
	MWA	0.088	88.7 ± 7.1	177.9			
	MWA	0.119	82.9 ± 6.6	75.3			
	MWA	0.155	68.9 ± 5.5	55.6			
	MWA	0.201	54.1 ± 4.4	49.0			
G021.8-0.6	MeerKAT	1.284	50.8 ± 4.1	0.21	-0.56	-0.56 ± 0.02	-0.45 ± 0.1
	MWA	0.088	190.1 ± 15.3	241.3			
	MWA	0.119	166.3 ± 13.3	116.5			
	MWA	0.155	131.2 ± 10.5	84.4			
	MWA	0.201	114.1 ± 9.1	52.0			
G022.7-0.2	MeerKAT	1.284	49.0 ± 3.9	0.67	-0.6	-0.34 ± 0.07	0.06 ± 0.15
	MWA	0.088	44.5 ± 4.0	310.0			
	MWA	0.119	43.1 ± 3.6	124.4			
	MWA	0.155	38.5 ± 3.2	76.4			
	MWA	0.201	39.9 ± 3.2	48.8			
G023.3-0.3	MeerKAT	1.284	69.7 ± 5.6	0.69	-0.5	-0.24 ± 0.06	-0.28 ± 0.23
	MWA	0.088	162.1 ± 13.2	399.1			
	MWA	0.119	149.0 ± 12.0	181.7			
	MWA	0.155	122.7 ± 9.9	110.7			
	MWA	0.201	113.1 ± 9.1	76.2			
G024.7-0.6	MeerKAT	1.284	9.9 ± 0.8	0.22	-0.5	-0.30 ± 0.04	-0.31 ± 0.14
	MWA	0.088	21.7 ± 2.0	179.8			
	MWA	0.119	22.2 ± 1.9	82.5			
	MWA	0.155	17.2 ± 1.4	54.7			
	MWA	0.201	15.9 ± 1.3	38.2			
G032.8-0.1	MeerKAT	1.284	12.1 ± 1.0	0.24	-0.2?	-0.45 ± 0.04	-0.41 ± 0.11
	MWA	0.088	42.1 ± 3.4	142.2			
	MWA	0.119	34.1 ± 2.8	81.2			
	MWA	0.155	27.4 ± 2.2	63.3			
	MWA	0.201	23.0 ± 1.9	45.2			
G033.2-0.6	MeerKAT	1.284	5.4 ± 0.4	0.21	-0.63 ¹	-0.45 ± 0.06	-0.29 ± 0.06
	MWA	0.088	11.1 ± 1.0	121.2			
	MWA	0.119	8.6 ± 0.8	83.1			
	MWA	0.155	8.4 ± 0.8	53.8			
	MWA	0.201	6.5 ± 0.6	39.4			
G035.6-0.4	MeerKAT	1.284	7.4 ± 0.8	0.22	-0.5	-0.20 ± 0.03	-0.19 ± 0.06
	MWA	0.088	10.0 ± 1.0	171.9			
	MWA	0.119	11.3 ± 1.0	101.9			
	MWA	0.155	11.1 ± 1.0	70.5			
	MWA	0.201	9.8 ± 0.8	45.5			
G040.5-0.5	MeerKAT	1.284	10.9 ± 0.5	0.16	-0.4	-0.26 ± 0.03	-0.18 ± 0.09
	MWA	0.088	20.3 ± 1.7	125.9			
	MWA	0.119	19.6 ± 1.6	86.4			
	MWA	0.155	13.7 ± 1.2	61.5			
	MWA	0.201	11.2 ± 1.0	39.9			

¹ Value from Dubner et al. (1996)

Table B.1. continued.

G045.7-0.4	MeerKAT	1.284	5.9 ± 0.5	0.143	-0.4?	-0.40 ± 0.04	-0.31 ± 0.14^2
	MWA	0.088	16.0 ± 1.4	123.1			
	MWA	0.119	14.2 ± 1.3	101.8			
	MWA	0.155	9.1 ± 0.9	53.6			
	MWA	0.201	7.8 ± 0.8	39.0			
G046.8-0.3	MeerKAT	1.284	18.2 ± 1.5	0.096	-0.54	-0.56 ± 0.04	-0.26 ± 0.8
	MWA	0.088	46.1 ± 3.8	190.0			
	MWA	0.119	37.4 ± 3.0	103.1			
	MWA	0.155	31.3 ± 2.5	54.0			
	MWA	0.201	27.7 ± 2.2	40.3			
G51.04+0.07³	MeerKAT	1.284	2.3 ± 0.2	0.4	-0.52	-0.33 ± 0.01	-0.29 ± 0.05
	MWA	0.155	3.6 ± 0.3	90.4			
G286.5-1.2	MeerKAT	1.284	1.5 ± 0.1	0.27	?	-0.60 ± 0.02	-0.44 ± 0.2
	MWA	0.088	7.3 ± 0.6	61.0			
	MWA	0.119	6.2 ± 0.5	39.4			
	MWA	0.155	5.1 ± 0.5	38.1			
	MWA	0.201	4.2 ± 0.4	19.5			
G289.7-0.3	MeerKAT	1.284	4.9 ± 0.4	0.25	-0.2?	-0.39 ± 0.03	-0.45 ± 0.07
	MWA	0.088	14.8 ± 1.2	82.8			
	MWA	0.119	14.2 ± 1.2	52.8			
	MWA	0.155	13.0 ± 1.1	31.7			
	MWA	0.201	11.5 ± 0.9	22.4			
G290.1-0.8	MeerKAT	1.284	34.8 ± 2.8	0.49	-0.4	-0.42 ± 0.03	-0.45 ± 0.1
	MWA	0.088	118.9 ± 9.5	151.7			
	MWA	0.119	109.4 ± 8.8	90.4			
	MWA	0.155	99.2 ± 7.9	40.3			
	MWA	0.201	91.0 ± 7.3	39.0			
G291.0-0.1	MeerKAT	1.284	21.6 ± 1.7	0.53	-0.29	-0.32 ± 0.02	-0.22 ± 0.24
	MWA	0.088	51.3 ± 4.1	56.4			
	MWA	0.119	47.2 ± 3.8	44.1			
	MWA	0.155	40.5 ± 3.3	25.5			
	MWA	0.201	37.1 ± 3.0	23.8			
G292.2-0.5	MeerKAT	1.284	10.7 ± 0.9	0.32	-0.5	-0.48 ± 0.01	-0.12 ± 0.19^4
	MWA	0.088	18.8 ± 1.6	105.9			
	MWA	0.119	17.6 ± 1.5	71.4			
	MWA	0.155	15.5 ± 1.3	38.2			
	MWA	0.201	12.8 ± 1.1	33.8			
G293.8+0.6	MeerKAT	1.284	3.9 ± 0.3	0.50	-0.6?	-0.34 ± 0.07	-0.25 ± 0.11
	MWA	0.088	8.1 ± 0.7	41.2			
	MWA	0.119	7.0 ± 0.6	26.1			
	MWA	0.155	6.3 ± 0.5	14.4			
	MWA	0.201	5.5 ± 0.5	13.0			
G296.7-0.9	MeerKAT	1.284	2.3 ± 0.2	0.15	-0.5	-0.35 ± 0.06	-0.34 ± 0.18
	MWA	0.088	5.8 ± 0.5	84.5			
	MWA	0.119	6.0 ± 0.5	52.7			
	MWA	0.155	4.8 ± 0.4	28.2			
	MWA	0.201	3.8 ± 0.3	22.7			
G296.8-0.3	MeerKAT	1.284	7.3 ± 0.6	0.28	-0.6	-0.60 ± 0.02	-0.59 ± 0.09
	MWA	0.088	3.5 ± 2.8	75.6			
	MWA	0.119	3.1 ± 2.5	41.2			
	MWA	0.155	2.7 ± 2.1	26.0			
	MWA	0.201	1.9 ± 1.5	26.2			
G301.4-1.0	MeerKAT	1.284	3.0 ± 0.2	0.17	?	-0.52 ± 0.08	-0.44 ± 0.11
	MWA	0.088	10.4 ± 0.9	65.4			
	MWA	0.119	9.1 ± 0.8	30.7			
	MWA	0.155	7.7 ± 0.6	19.7			
	MWA	0.201	7.3 ± 0.6	18.4			

² Value obtained by excluding the H II regions from the spectral index map.

³ All values are obtained by considering the extraction region from Supan et al. 2018

⁴ The spectral index value is calculated by including the flat-central region where there is no emission from the remnant.

Table B.1. continued.

G332.4+0.1	MeerKAT	1.284	20.9 ± 1.7	0.52	-0.5	-0.57 ± 0.07	-0.47 ± 0.12
	MWA	0.088	66.3 ± 5.4	268.3			
	MWA	0.119	66.8 ± 5.4	91.2			
	MWA	0.155	56.7 ± 4.6	67.3			
	MWA	0.201	48.3 ± 3.9	55.1			
G335.2+0.1	MeerKAT	1.284	12.6 ± 1.0	0.12	-0.5	-0.47 ± 0.03	-0.50 ± 0.09
	MWA	0.088	55.2 ± 4.5	213.8			
	MWA	0.119	45.2 ± 3.7	85.7			
	MWA	0.155	36.5 ± 2.9	45.5			
	MWA	0.201	29.0 ± 2.4	46.4			
G337.3+1.0	MeerKAT	1.284	11.4 ± 0.9	0.10	-0.55	-0.48 ± 0.05	-0.48 ± 0.08
	MWA	0.088	47.8 ± 3.9	128.2			
	MWA	0.119	38.5 ± 3.1	73.9			
	MWA	0.155	32.9 ± 2.6	41.7			
	MWA	0.201	27.3 ± 2.2	35.2			
G348.7+0.3	MeerKAT	1.284	34.5 ± 2.8	0.48	-0.3	-0.36 ± 0.03	-0.35 ± 0.18
	MWA	0.088	79.7 ± 6.5	336.0			
	MWA	0.119	81.3 ± 6.5	107.8			
	MWA	0.155	68.1 ± 5.5	82.1			
	MWA	0.201	59.0 ± 4.8	58.8			
G351.7+0.8	MeerKAT	1.284	6.4 ± 0.5	0.32	-0.5?	-0.37 ± 0.06	-0.41 ± 14
	MWA	0.088	21.7 ± 2.0	262.4			
	MWA	0.119	21.2 ± 1.7	59.9			
	MWA	0.155	16.3 ± 1.3	43.0			
	MWA	0.201	13.1 ± 1.1	41.9			
G351.9+0.1	MeerKAT	1.284	2.6 ± 0.2	0.20	-0.99 ⁵	-0.47 ± 0.04	-0.34 ± 20
	MWA	0.088	9.3 ± 1.0	196.3			
	MWA	0.119	8.8 ± 0.8	85.3			
	MWA	0.155	6.1 ± 0.6	44.6			
	MWA	0.201	6.1 ± 0.6	42.4			

⁵ Spectral value from Hurley-Walker et al. (2019).

Table B.2. Flux density measurements from the literature we used to study the integrated spectrum of each SNR. The instrument or the survey by which they were acquired and related references are also reported respectively in the fourth and fifth columns (when available).

Source name	Freq. (GHz)	Flux density (Jy)	Telescope	Reference
G003.8+0.3	0.327	6.0 ± 0.4	GMRT	Bhatnagar (2002)
	0.843	3.5 ± 0.4	MOST	Gray (1994)
G018.8+0.3	0.031	87.4 ± 17.5	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.080	94.5 ± 14.2	Culgoora radioheliograph	Slee & Higgins (1973)
	0.080	157.3 ± 50.0	Culgoora radioheliograph	Dickel (1973)
	0.083	87.0 ± 20.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.111	80.0 ± 20.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.333	55.3 ± 16.6	VLA	Kassim (1992)
	0.408	36.9 ± 3.7	Parkes	Clark et al. (1975)
	0.408	38.4 ± 3.9	Molonglo	Kesteven (1968)
	0.960	28.0 ± 2.8	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.414	33.3 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	1.465	29.9 ± 0.3	VLA	Dubner et al. (1996)
	2.695	18.8 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.7	12.4 ± 1.2	Parkes	Goss & Day (1970)
	2.7	17.2 ± 7.0	NRAO 300ft	Willis (1973)
	2.7	22.7 ± 3.4	Parkes	Milne & Dickel (1974)
	3.65	18.0 ± 1.8	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	3.9	18.9 ± 1.9	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	4.85	16.6 ± 1.6	PMN	Kuchar & Clark (1997)
	4.875	23.4 ± 2.3	Effelsberg	Downes et al. (1980)
	5.0	12.4 ± 0.4	Ft.Davis	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
5.0	15.7 ± 2.4	Parkes	Milne & Hill (1969)	
5.0	19.2 ± 1.9	Parkes	Milne & Dickel (1975a)	
8.4	12.9 ± 0.3	Parkes	Milne et al. (1989)	
G021.8-0.6	0.0299	210.0 ± 40.0	Fleurs	Jones & Finlay (1974)
	0.0309	170.6 ± 34.1	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.0575	168.0 ± 33.6	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.08	103.1 ± 10.3	Culgora	Slee & Higgins (1973)
	0.08	320.1 ± 100	Culgora	Dickel (1973)
	0.083	210 ± 40	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.111	180.0 ± 40	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.330	132.2 ± 26.4	VLA	Kassim (1992)
	0.408	68.9 ± 6.9	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	0.408	106.7 ± 10.7	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970a)
	0.408	180.6 ± 18.1	Molonglo	Kesteven (1968)
	0.960	63.0 ± 6.3	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.414	46.5 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	1.660	41.5 ± 4.2	Parkes	Milne & Hill (1969)
	2.695	29.7 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.7	31.3 ± 3.1	NRAO 300ft	Willis (1973)
	2.7	39.0 ± 3.9	Parkes	Goss & Day (1970)
	2.7	40.2 ± 8.0	Parkes	Milne & Dickel (1974)
	2.7	41.0 ± 4.1	Parkes	Milne & Hill (1969)
	2.7	42.8 ± 4.6	NRAO 300f	Velusamy & Kundu (1974a)
	3.650	30.0 ± 3.0	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	3.9	28.0 ± 2.8	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	4.875	27.6 ± 2.8	Effelsberg	Downes et al. (1980)
	5.0	16.7 ± 1.7	Parkes	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	5.0	20.6 ± 0.4	Ft.Davis	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	5.0	24.0 ± 2.4	NRAO 140ft	Kundu et al. (1974)
	5.0	29.1 ± 2.9	Parkes	Shaver & Goss (1970a)
5.0	31.2 ± 3.1	Parkes	Milne & Dickel (1975b)	
5.0	24.03 ± 1.29	Urumqi 25-m	Sun et al. (2011)	
8.35	14.31 ± 0.8	GBES ⁶	Langston et al. (2000)	
10.7	14.0 ± 1.4	NRAO 140ft	Kundu et al. (1974)	

⁶ NRAO-NASA Green Bank Earth Station

Table B.2. continued.

Source name	Freq. (GHz)	Flux density (Jy)	Telescope	Reference
	14.35	5.31 ± 0.4	GBES ⁷	Langston et al. (2000)
G022.7-00.2	0.058	37.5 ± 7.5	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.102	130.0 ± 20	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.330	82.0 ± 16.0	VLA	Kassim (1992)
	0.408	53.4 ± 5.3	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	1.414	66.7 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.695	50.5 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	5.0	28.8 ± 2.8	Parkes	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	5.0	42.2 ± 0.4	Ft.Davis	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
G023.3-00.3	0.058	57.7 ± 11.5	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.080	35.4 ± 3.5	Culgoora radioheliograph	Slee & Higgins (1973)
	0.083	134.0 ± 30.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.111	146.0 ± 30.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.330	151.0 ± 30.2	VLA	Kassim (1992)
	0.408	109.3 ± 10.9	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	0.408	146.8 ± 14.7	Molonglo	Kesteven (1968)
	0.408	228.9 ± 22.9	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	1.414	50.5 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.695	35.6 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.7	92.7 ± 9.3	Parkes	Goss & Day (1970)
	5.0	24.7 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	5.0	47.8 ± 4.8	Parkes	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
5.0	61.1 ± 6.1	Parkes	Shaver & Goss (1970b)	
G024.7-00.6	0.0309	11.3 ± 2.3	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.102	13.0 ± 2.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.408	11.9 ± 1.2	Molonglo	Clark et al. (1975)
	0.960	7.5 ± 0.8	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.414	6.1 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.695	3.0 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	3.9	2.6 ± 0.3	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	5.0	2.2 ± 0.5	NRAO 140ft	Angerhofer et al. (1977)
	5.0	$3.6 \pm$	Parkes	Clark et al. (1975)
G032.8-00.1	0.031	64.5 ± 12.9	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.083	23.0 ± 5.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.111	24.0 ± 5.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.330	31.3 ± 6.3	VLA	Kassim (1992)
	0.408	12.4 ± 1.2	Molonglo	Caswell et al. (1975)
	0.430	20.0 ± 15.5	Arecibo	Dickel & Denoyer (1975)
	0.960	5.6 ± 0.6	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.4	10.9 ± 1.1	VLA	Dokara et al. (2023)
	2.965	5.9 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.7	7.3 ± 0.5	NRAO 300ft	Velusamy & Kundu (1974b)
	2.7	7.3 ± 0.8	Effelsberg	Dokara et al. (2023)
	3.9	5.5 ± 0.6	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	5.0	7.7 ± 0.8	Parkes	Caswell et al. (1975)
	5.8	6.5 ± 0.9	VLA+Effelsberg	Dokara et al. (2023)
10.5	5.9 ± 0.7	Nobeyama	Dokara et al. (2023)	
10.6	2.8 ± 0.6	NRAO 140ft	Becker & Kundu (1975)	
G033.2-0.6	0.031	44.1 ± 8.8	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.102	16.5 ± 5.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	1.4	2.0 ± 0.2	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.465	2.7 ± 1.0	VLA	Dubner et al. (1996)
	2.7	2.6 ± 0.3	Effelsberg	Reich (1982)
	4.75	1.75 ± 0.2	Effelsberg	Reich (1982)
G035.6-00.4	1.4	7.8 ± 0.8	VLA	Green (2009)
	1.4	8.8 ± 0.9	VLA	Dokara et al. (2023)
	2.7	7.5 ± 0.8	Effelsberg	Dokara et al. (2023)
	5.8	6.0 ± 0.6	VLA	Dokara et al. (2023)

⁷ NRAO-NASA Green Bank Earth Station

Table B.2. continued.

Source name	Freq. (GHz)	Flux density (Jy)	Telescope	Reference
	10.0	3.1 ± 0.3	Nobeyama	Green (2009)
	10.5	4.7 ± 0.5	Nobeyama	Dokara et al. (2023)
G040.5-00.5	0.031	6.3 ± 1.3	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.083	33.0 ± 5.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.111	34.0 ± 5.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.750	12.3 ± 3.2	NRAO 300ft	Pauliny-Toth et al. (1966)
	0.960	10.0 ± 1.0	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.4	10.2 ± 1.6	NRAO 300ft	Pauliny-Toth et al. (1966)
	1.414	8.1 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	1.720	9.3 ± 1.3	Effelsberg	Downes et al. (1980)
	2.695	5.9 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.7	7.2 ± 0.5	Effelsberg	Downes et al. (1980)
	3.9	8.6 ± 0.9	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	5.0	6.39 ± 0.34	Urumqi 25-m	Sun et al. (2011)
	8.35	3.58 ± 0.2	NRAO 300ft	Langston et al. (2000)
G045.7-00.4	0.102	11.0 ± 6.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.327	16.27 ± 0.1	WSRT	Taylor et al. (1992)
	0.960	12.6 ± 1.3	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.42	3.9 ± 0.4	Bonn	Fuerst et al. (1987)
	2.695	3.2 ± 0.3	Bonn	Fuerst et al. (1987)
	3.9	4.0 ± 0.4	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	4.75	2.6 ± 0.3	Bonn	Fuerst et al. (1987)
	10.55	2.2 ± 0.3	Bonn	Fuerst et al. (1987)
	11.2	1.5 ± 0.2	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
G046.8-00.3	0.0309	93.9 ± 18.8	CLRO	Kassim (1988)
	0.038	102.9 ± 10.3	WKB	Holden & Caswell (1969)
	0.080	43.0 ± 0.4	Culgoora radioheliograph	Slee & Higgins (1973)
	0.080	111.1 ± 50.0	Culgoora radioheliograph	Dickel (1973)
	0.083	58.0 ± 10.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.111	55.0 ± 10.0	BSA,DKR	Kovalenko et al. (1994)
	0.178	46.6 ± 4.7	Pencil Beam	Caswell_1969 & Crowther (1969)
	0.327	41.12 ± 1.00	WSRT	Taylor et al. (1992)
	0.408	19.6 ± 2.0	Molonglo	Caswell et al. (1975)
	0.408	24.8 ± 2.5	-	Holden & Caswell (1969)
	0.430	48.3 ± 21.0	Arecibo	Dickel & Denoyer (1975)
	0.610	23.4 ± 2.3	-	Holden & Caswell (1969)
	0.750	27.9 ± 2.8	NRAO 300ft	Holden & Caswell (1969)
	0.960	15.80 ± 1.6	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	1.4	18.9 ± 1.9	NRAO 300ft	Holden & Caswell (1969)
	1.414	17.2 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	1.465	13.3 ± 0.10	VLA	Dubner et al. (1996)
	1.665	15.4 ± 5.5	VRO 37m	Willis (1973)
	2.695	10.0 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	2.7	6.5 ± 0.7	-	Holden & Caswell (1969)
	2.7	10.1 ± 1.0	Parkes	Day et al. (1970)
	2.7	10.9 ± 1.1	NRAO 300ft	Willis (1973)
	3.9	9.0 ± 0.9	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	4.8	7.17 ± 0.37	WRST	Taylor et al. (1992)
	5.0	5.2 ± 0.5	NRAO 140ft	Angerhofer et al. (1977)
	5.0	7.1 ± 0.7	Parkes	Caswell et al. (1975)
	11.2	5.3 ± 0.5	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
G051.21+0.11	-	-	-	-
G286.5-01.2	0.843	1.6 ± 0.2	Molonglo	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
G289.7-00.3	0.408	9.7 ± 1.0	Molonglo	Green (1974)
	0.843	6.4 ± 0.5	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	4.5	7.5 ± 2.5	Parkes	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	8.55	3.6 ± 0.9	Parkes	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
G290.1-0.8	0.0299	35.0 ± 7.0	Fleurs	Jones & Finlay (1974)
	0.085	162.0 ± 16.2	Sydney 3.5 m cross-type radio telescope	Mills et al. (1960)
	0.408	99.1 ± 9.9	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970b)

Table B.2. continued.

Source name	Freq. (GHz)	Flux density (Jy)	Telescope	Reference
	0.843	45.0 ± 11.0	MOST	Milne et al. (1989)
	0.843	43.0 ± 4.3	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	2.650	20.0 ± 2.0	Parkes	KES13?
	5.0	20.2 ± 2.0	Parkes	Milne & Dickel (1975a)
	8.4	19.5 ± 1.0	Parkes	Milne et al. (1989)
	8.8	19.5 ± 1.1	Parkes	Dickel (1973)
G291.0-0.1	0.085	42.0 ± 4.2	Sydney 3.5 m cross-type radio telescope	Mills et al. (1960)
	0.408	24.3 ± 2.4	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	0.408	32.2 ± 3.2	Molonglo	Green (1974)
	0.843	17.2 ± 1.0	MOST	Roger et al. (1986)
	0.843	12.7 ± 1.3	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	2.65	15 ± 1.5	Parkes	Thomas & Day (1969a)
	5.0	9.2 ± 0.5	Parkes	Goss & Day (1970)
	5.0	8.4 ± 0.8	Parkes	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	5.0	9.1 ± 0.1	Parkes	Roger et al. (1986)
	8.4	10.4 ± 0.4	Parkes	Roger et al. (1986)
G292.2-0.5	1.4	5.6 ± 0.3	ATCA	Crawford et al. (2001)
	5.0	2.8 ± 0.2	ATCA	Caswell et al. (2004)
G293.8+0.6	0.408	9.0 ± 0.9	Molonglo	Clark et al. (1975)
	0.843	2.6 ± 0.3	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	2.65	2.0 ± 0.2	Parkes	Thomas & Day (1969a)
	5.0	2.1 ± 0.2	Parkes	Clark et al. (1975)
G296.7-0.9	0.843	2.9 ± 0.3	MOST	Green (2014)
	1.4	2.5 ± 0.2	ATCA	Robbins et al. (2012)
G296.8-0.3	0.03	93.0 ± 20.0	Fleurs	Jones & Finlay (1974)
	0.408	15.0 ± 1.5	Molonglo	Caswell et al. (1975)
	0.843	9.2 ± 0.9	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	1.344	7.0 ± 0.3	ATCA	Gaensler et al. (1998)
	1.42	6.0 ± 1.0	Parkes	Large & Vaughan (1972)
	2.695	4.0 ± 1.0	Parkes	Thomas & Day (1969a)
	5.0	3.2 ± 1.0	Parkes	Caswell et al. (1975)
G301.4-1.0	0.843	2.3 ± 0.2	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
G332.4+0.1	0.086	256.0 ± 25.6	MSH	Holden & Caswell (1969)
	0.408	28.0 ± 2.8	Molonglo	Kesteven (1968)
	0.408	19.8 ± 2.0	Molonglo	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
	0.843	29.0 ± 3.0	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	1.41	9.7 ± 1.0	-	Trushkin (1999)
	5.0	7.0 ± 0.7	Parkes	Shaver & Goss (1970b)
G335.2+0.1	0.408	27.1 ± 2.7	Molonglo	Clark et al. (1975)
	0.843	16.0 ± 1.6	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	5.0	8.6 ± 0.9	Parkes	Clark et al. (1975)
G337.3+1.0	0.408	24.6 ± 2.5	Molonglo	Green (1974)
	0.408	18.0 ± 1.8	Molonglo	Kesteven (1968)
	0.843	20.0 ± 2.0	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	0.843	14.8 ± 3.0	MOST	Milne et al. (1989)
	1.41	8.1 ± 0.8	-	Trushkin (1999)
	2.65	5.0 ± 0.5	Parkes	Thomas & Day (1969b)
	5.0	7.2 ± 0.7	Parkes	Caswell et al. (1975)
	5.0	10.0 ± 1.0	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	8.4	5.1 ± 0.6	Parkes	Milne et al. (1989)
G348.7+0.3	0.08	35.4 ± 3.5	Culgoora radiotelescope	Kassim et al. (1991)
	0.08	46.0 ± 12.0	Culgoora radiotelescope	Kassim et al. (1991)
	0.160	40.7 ± 4.1	Culgoora radiotelescope	Kassim et al. (1991)
	0.160	47.0 ± 4.7	Culgoora radiotelescope	Kassim et al. (1991)
	0.333	55.2 ± 2.9	VLA	Kassim et al. (1991)
	0.408	40.6 ± 6.1	Molonglo	Kassim et al. (1991)
	0.408	34.4 ± 3.4	Molonglo	Clark et al. (1975)
	0.843	33.0 ± 3.3	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	1.41	30.8 ± 4.0	VLA	Kassim et al. (1991)
	2.65	21.2 ± 2.1	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)

Table B.2. continued.

Source name	Freq. (GHz)	Flux density (Jy)	Telescope	Reference
	2.65	28.8 ± 2.9	Parkes	Milne & Hill (1969)
	2.695	21.8 ± 0.4	NRAO 140ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	3.9	21.0 ± 2.1	RATAN	Trushkin (1996)
	5.0	14.4 ± 0.4	NRAO 300ft	Altenhoff et al. (1970)
	5.0	22.9 ± 2.3	Parkes	Milne & Hill (1969)
	5.0	33.3 ± 3.3	Parkes	Milne & Dickel (1975a)
	8.8	20.1 ± 2.0	Parkes	Dickel (1973)
	14.7	18.4 ± 5.8	Molonglo	Milne & Hill (1969)
G351.7+0.8	0.843	11.0 ± 1.1	MOST	Whiteoak & Green (1996)
	1.4	8.4 ± 0.7	ATCA	Tian et al. (2007)
G351.9+0.1	-	-	-	-

References

- Altenhoff, W. J., Downes, D., Goad, L., Maxwell, A., & Rinehart, R. 1970, *A&AS*, 1, 319
- Anderson, L. D., Armentrout, W. P., Johnstone, B. M., et al. 2015, *ApJS*, 221, 26
- Anderson, L. D., Bania, T. M., Balser, D. S., et al. 2014, *ApJS*, 212, 1
- Anderson, L. D., Bania, T. M., Balser, D. S., & Rood, R. T. 2011, *ApJS*, 194, 32
- Angerhofer, P. E., Becker, R. H., & Kundu, M. R. 1977, *A&A*, 55, 11
- Becker, R. H. & Kundu, M. R. 1975, *AJ*, 80, 679
- Bhatnagar, S. 2002, *MNRAS*, 332, 1
- Caswell, J. L., Clark, D. H., & Crawford, D. F. 1975, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 37, 39
- Caswell, J. L., McClure-Griffiths, N. M., & Cheung, M. C. M. 2004, *MNRAS*, 352, 1405
- Caswell_1969, J. L. & Crowther, J. H. 1969, *MNRAS*, 145, 181
- Clark, D. H., Caswell, J. L., & Green, A. J. 1975, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 37, 1
- Crawford, F., Gaensler, B. M., Kaspi, V. M., et al. 2001, *ApJ*, 554, 152
- Day, G. A., Warne, W. G., & Cooke, D. J. 1970, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 13, 11
- Dickel, J. R. 1973, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 26, 369
- Dickel, J. R. & Denoyer, L. K. 1975, *AJ*, 80, 437
- Dokara, R., Gong, Y., Reich, W., et al. 2023, *A&A*, 671, A145
- Downes, D., Wilson, T. L., Bieging, J., & Wink, J. 1980, *A&AS*, 40, 379
- Dubner, G. M., Giacani, E. B., Goss, W. M., Moffett, D. A., & Holdaway, M. 1996, *AJ*, 111, 1304
- Fuerst, E., Reich, W., Reich, P., Handa, T., & Sofue, Y. 1987, *A&AS*, 69, 403
- Gaensler, B. M., Manchester, R. N., & Green, A. J. 1998, *MNRAS*, 296, 813
- Goss, W. M. & Day, G. A. 1970, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 13, 3
- Gray, A. D. 1994, *MNRAS*, 270, 847
- Green, A. J. 1974, *A&AS*, 18, 267
- Green, D. A. 2009, *MNRAS*, 399, 177
- Green, D. A. 2014, *Bulletin of the Astronomical Society of India*, 42, 47
- Green, D. A. 2022, Cavendish Laboratory, Cambridge, United Kingdom
- Holden, D. J. & Caswell, J. L. 1969, *MNRAS*, 143, 407
- Hurley-Walker, N., Filipović, M. D., Gaensler, B. M., et al. 2019, *PASA*, 36, e045
- Jones, B. B. & Finlay, E. A. 1974, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 27, 687
- Kassim, N. E. 1988, *ApJS*, 68, 715
- Kassim, N. E. 1992, *AJ*, 103, 943
- Kassim, N. E., Baum, S. A., & Weiler, K. W. 1991, *ApJ*, 374, 212
- Kesteven, M. J. L. 1968, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 21, 369
- Kovalenko, A. V., Pynzar', A. V., & Udal'Tsov, V. A. 1994, *Astronomy Reports*, 38, 78
- Kuchar, T. A. & Clark, F. O. 1997, *ApJ*, 488, 224
- Kundu, M. R., Velusamy, T., & Hardee, P. E. 1974, *AJ*, 79, 132
- Langston, G., Minter, A., D'Addario, L., et al. 2000, *AJ*, 119, 2801
- Large, M. I. & Vaughan, A. E. 1972, *Nature Physical Science*, 236, 117
- Mills, B. Y., Slee, O. B., & Hill, E. R. 1960, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 13, 676
- Milne, D. K., Caswell, J. L., Kesteven, M. J., Haynes, R. F., & Roger, R. S. 1989, *PASA*, 8, 187
- Milne, D. K. & Dickel, J. R. 1974, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 27, 549
- Milne, D. K. & Dickel, J. R. 1975a, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 28, 209
- Milne, D. K. & Dickel, J. R. 1975b, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 28, 209
- Milne, D. K. & Hill, E. R. 1969, *Australian Journal of Physics*, 22, 211
- Pauliny-Toth, I. I. K., Wade, C. M., & Heeschen, D. S. 1966, *ApJS*, 13, 65
- Reich, W. 1982, *A&A*, 106, 314
- Robbins, W. J., Gaensler, B. M., Murphy, T., Reeves, S., & Green, A. J. 2012, *MNRAS*, 419, 2623
- Roger, R. S., Costain, C. H., & Stewart, D. I. 1986, *A&AS*, 65, 485
- Sewilo, M., Watson, C., Araya, E., et al. 2004, *ApJS*, 154, 553
- Shaver, P. A. & Goss, W. M. 1970a, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 14, 77
- Shaver, P. A. & Goss, W. M. 1970b, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 14, 133
- Slee, O. B. & Higgins, C. S. 1973, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 27, 1
- Sun, X. H., Reich, W., Han, J. L., et al. 2011, *A&A*, 527, A74
- Supan, L., Castelletti, G., Peters, W. M., & Kassim, N. E. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A98
- Taylor, A. R., Wallace, B. J., & Goss, W. M. 1992, *AJ*, 103, 931
- Thomas, B. M. & Day, G. A. 1969a, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 11, 3
- Thomas, B. M. & Day, G. A. 1969b, *Australian Journal of Physics Astrophysical Supplement*, 11, 19
- Tian, W. W., Li, Z., Leahy, D. A., & Wang, Q. D. 2007, *ApJ*, 657, L25
- Trushkin, S. A. 1996, *Bulletin of the Special Astrophysics Observatory*, 41, 64
- Trushkin, S. A. 1999, *Odessa Astronomical Publications*, 12, 144
- Velusamy, T. & Kundu, M. R. 1974a, *A&A*, 32, 375
- Velusamy, T. & Kundu, M. R. 1974b, *A&A*, 32, 375
- Whiteoak, J. B. Z. & Green, A. J. 1996, *A&AS*, 118, 329
- Willis, A. G. 1973, *A&A*, 26, 237